

Aromatic Character of Borazole and Substituted Borazole

Chandra Bhusan Chowdhury and Rama Basu

The aromatic characters of borazole and substituted borazoles have been examined from the theoretical calculations on the shift in the longest wave length absorption band and resonance energies of the substituted borazoles. Borazole shows about 50% aromatic character in agreement with the experimental work.

Borazole with the alternate boron and nitrogen atom in hexagon is often called inorganic benzene. It shows its aromaticity in many respects such as equal bond length, high resonance energy etc. In order to see whether the spectral shift due to substitution in different positions in borazole can be explained by inductive and mesomeric effect as is present in aromatic systems, calculations were done by the usual Longuet-Higgins and Sowden's¹ method in different substituted borazoles.

Simple Huckel calculation was done on borazole molecule. The following Coulomb integrals and resonance integrals are used:

$$\begin{aligned} \alpha_N &= \alpha_C + 0.2\beta \\ \alpha_B &= \alpha_C - 0.2\beta \\ \beta_{B-N} &= 0.7\beta_{C-C} \end{aligned}$$

α_C being the Coulomb integrals for aromatic carbon and β_{C-C} the resonance integral for carbon-carbon bond in aromatic system. The Huckel orbitals and coefficients for borazole molecule are given in appendix.

The principle underlying Longuet-Higgins and Sowden's method is well established and explained elsewhere. ($\Delta\epsilon_{ab}$) total is calculated by summing the contribution due to ($\Delta\epsilon_{ab}$) inductive and ($\Delta\epsilon_{ab}$) hyperconjugative and is given by the formulae

$$(\Delta\epsilon_{ab})_{\text{total}} = (\Delta\epsilon_{ab})_{\text{inductive}} + (\Delta\epsilon_{ab})_{\text{hyperconjugative}} \quad \dots \quad (1)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &= (C_{br}^2 - C_{ar}^2) \delta \alpha_r + \left(\sum_{j \neq b} \frac{C_{br}^2 C_{jr}^2}{\epsilon_b - \epsilon_j} - \sum_{j \neq a} \frac{C_{ar}^2 C_{jr}^2}{\epsilon_a - \epsilon_j} \right) (\delta \alpha_r)^2 \\ &+ \beta_{rs}^2 \left(\sum_{k \neq b} \frac{C_{br}^2 C_{ks}^2}{\epsilon_b - \epsilon_k} - \sum_{k \neq a} \frac{C_{ar}^2 C_{ks}^2}{\epsilon_a - \epsilon_k} \right) \quad \dots \quad (2) \end{aligned}$$

$$= (\epsilon_b' - \epsilon_a') - (\epsilon_b - \epsilon_a) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

where primed quantities refer to the substituted borazole and unprimed to borazole molecule. The first two quantities in expression (2) refer to inductive effect and the last one to the mesomeric effect. C_{jr} refers to atomic orbital coefficient of the r^{th} carbon in the

j^{th} molecular orbital $\delta \propto r$ the alteration in the Coulomb integral, β_{rs} is the resonance integral of the bond formed between the r^{th} atom of borazole and s^{th} atom of the substituent.

Calculation was done on methyl substituted and phenyl substituted borazole. The Coulomb and resonance parameters used for methyl group ($-\text{C}\equiv\text{H}_3$) are $E_{\text{C}}=E_0-0.1\beta$, $\beta_{\text{ms}}=2.5\beta$, $E_{\text{H}_3}=E_0-0.5\beta$. The energy levels and atomic orbital coefficients for phenyl group were taken from Dictionary of Values of Molecular Constants, Vol II (C.A. Coulson and R. Daudel).

For the phenyl substituent use was made of Dewar's² modified formula for molecules containing degenerate levels.

As there will not be any inductive effect due to the introduction of phenyl group, the formula for hyperconjugative effect was modified as below:

For the combined system RS, suppose R has a degenerate level E_u , corresponding to the y MO's Φ^x_u ($x=1, 2, \dots, y$). The secular equation for RS can be reduced to the form

$$(W - E_u)^{y-1} \left\{ \pi_m (W - E_m) \pi_n (W - F_n) \left[1 - \sum_{m,n} \frac{C^2_{mrb^2_{ns}} \beta^2_{rs}}{(W - E_m)(W - F_n)} \right] \right\} = 0 \quad (4)$$

where $C_{mr} = a_{mr}$ ($m \neq u$)

$$C_{ur} = \left[\sum_x (a^x_{ur})^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

If there were no degeneracy, the secular equation for RS would be

$$\pi_m (W - E_m) \pi_n (W - F_n) \left\{ 1 - \sum_{mn} \frac{a^2_{mr} b^2_{ns} \beta^2_{rs}}{(W - E_m)(W - F_n)} \right\} = 0 \quad \dots \quad (5)$$

Comparison of (5) with (4) shows that in the degenerate case the set of MO's Φ^x_u has been replaced by linear combinations (as is always allowable for degenerate levels) such that in the modified MO's the coefficients C_{ur} of the AO Φ_r are given by

$$C^x_{ur} = 0 \quad [x=1, 2, \dots, (y-1)]$$

$$C^y_{ur} = \left[\sum_x (a^x_{ur})^2 \right]^{\frac{1}{2}}$$

Thus the second order perturbation values for the y levels C^x_u of RS corresponding to the levels E_u of R are

$$G^x_u = E_u \quad [x=1, 2, \dots, (y-1)]$$

$$G^y_u = E_u + \sum_n \frac{[\sum_x (a^x_{ur})^2] b^2_{ns} \beta^2_{rs}}{E_u - F_n}$$

However, since for the phenyl ring the atomic orbital coefficients for one of the doubly degenerate levels are zero, the equation becomes quite simple.

The different values taken for β_{r_s} at different positions of the parent molecule are
 $\beta_{CN} = 0.8 \beta$ when methyl group is attached to nitrogen atom of borazole ring;
 $= 0.5 \beta$ when phenyl group is attached to nitrogen atom of borazole ring.
 $\beta_{CB} = 0.7 \beta$ when methyl group is attached to boron atom of borazole ring;
 $= 0.4 \beta$ when phenyl group is attached to boron atom of borazole ring.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

$(\Delta \epsilon_{ab})_{total}$ calculated is given in Table I for the methyl substituted borazole. The calculated data shows good agreement where the experimental ones are available. Unfortunately very few experimental data are available.

TABLE I

Calculated and experimental spectral shift in methyl borazole

$$(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_b) = -1.4560 \beta$$

Compound	$(\Delta \epsilon)_{ab \text{ induc}}$	$(\Delta \epsilon)_{ab \text{ hypercon}}$	$(\Delta \epsilon)_{ab \text{ total}}$	$(\Delta \lambda)_{m\mu \text{ calc.}}$	$(\Delta \lambda)_{m\mu \text{ obs.}}$
N-trimethyl	0.0271 β	0.1044 β	0.1315 β	29.7	28.19 ³
B-trimethyl	-0.0278 β	0.0534 β	0.0255 β	5.3	8.75 ³
Hexamethyl	-0.0007 β	0.1577 β	0.1570 β	36.1	

For the phenyl substituted borazole, no experimental data is available. However, the calculated results are given in Table II and can be compared with the experimental results whenever it will be available.

TABLE II

Calculated spectral shift in phenyl substituted borazoles.

$$(\epsilon_a - \epsilon_b) = -1.4560 \beta$$

Compound	$(\Delta \epsilon)_{ab \text{ induc}}$	$(\Delta \epsilon)_{ab \text{ hypercon}}$	$(\Delta \epsilon)_{ab \text{ total}}$	$(\Delta \lambda)_{m\mu \text{ calc.}}$	$(\Delta \lambda)_{m\mu \text{ obs.}}$
N-triphenyl	0.0	0.1980 β	0.198 β	48	
B-triphenyl	0.0	0.2270 β	0.2270 β	55	

The good agreement for the trimethyl borazole with the experimental results show that both the inductive and hyperconjugative effect exist in borazole indicating that it possesses some aromatic character. The experimental shift in phenyl substituted borazoles is not available but there is an indirect proof about the phenyl ring entering in the conjugation with borazole. Thus the 260 $m\mu$ absorption of benzene shows a red shift indicating that the phenyl ring does enter in conjugation with borazole ring.

Following the same procedure, resonance energies for the different substituted borazoles were calculated and are tabulated in Table III. Since the contribution of the mesomeric effect should be predominant in resonance energy this effect only is taken into consideration.

TABLE III

Resonance energies of borazole and methyl and phenyl substituted borazoles.

Compound	Resonance energy/ β
Borazole	1.3724
N-methyl borazole	1.2971
B-methyl borazole	1.3200
N-trimethyl borazole	1.1466
B-trimethyl borazole	1.2155
N-phenyl borazole	1.5565
B-phenyl borazole	1.4482
N-triphenyl borazole	1.9246
B-triphenyl borazole	1.3835
Hexamethyl borazole	0.9897
Hexaphenyl borazole	1.9678

According to Platt from UV-spectra borazole should have 50% aromatic character when compared to benzene. The resonance energy calculation on borazole when compared to that of benzene (benzene has a resonance energy of 2β) also shows that borazole has a little more than 50% aromatic character (1.37β) when other substituted borazoles are compared it is found however that the correspondence of resonance energies to stability is not so good. From the thermochemical data the order of stability observed⁴ is as follows:

B-triphenyl N-trimethyl borazole < hexa-phenyl borazole < B-trimethyl N-triphenyl < B-triphenyl < hexamethyl borazole.

One of the reasons for this is that stability data is derived from thermochemical data which may involve the change both in the σ -bond and π -bond of the molecule where as in deriving the resonance energies only the π -bonds have been considered here. However the data for trimethyl substituted borazoles show good agreement with the stability data i.e., hexamethyl borazole < N-trimethyl borazole < B-trimethyl borazole.

Unfortunately the heat of hydrogenation data is not available which is more likely to give a good measure of resonance energies.

APPENDIX

Atomic orbital coefficients of Borazole molecule. The x direction is 1→4 in the borazole molecule.

Energy levels	Symmetry	C ₍₁₎	C ₍₂₎	C ₍₃₎	C ₍₄₎
$E_0 + 1.4142\beta$	S _x	0.4362	0.3783	0.4362	0.3782
$E_0 + 0.7280\beta$	S _x	0.6518	0.2458	-0.3259	-0.4917
$E_0 + 0.7280\beta$	A _x	0	0.4258	0.5645	0
$E_0 - 0.7280\beta$	S _x	-0.4917	0.3259	0.2458	0.6518
$E_0 - 0.7280\beta$	A _x	0	0.5645	-0.4258	0
$E_0 - 1.4142\beta$	S _x	-0.3783	0.4362	-0.3783	0.4362

DEPARTMENT OF PURE CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY COLLEGE OF SCIENCE,
CALCUTTA-9.

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